

Supporting Information

S1 Appendix. Selection criteria

Three ELN systems are defined below, and criteria to consider when selecting an ELN are listed for each system.

Basic ELNs

Basic ELNs are tools that are used as ELNs but that were not originally developed for this purpose (e.g., Word, Evernote, Dropbox) [15]. They allow for traditional text entries that can be searched and made available via the cloud. They also allow files to be attached, viewed, annotated and searched.

Specialised ELNs

Specialised ELNs are tools that allow unstructured data entry and offer an extensive range of functionalities (e.g., eLabJournal, eLabFTW, Labfolder) [15]. In addition to all the features of basic ELNs, they also have the ability to capture freehand and chemical drawings [8] and offer subject-specific features/editors and templates. Moreover, they enable task assignment to multiple individuals, complex rights management, basic inventory management (i.e. allowing the quantity and location of samples and reagents to be managed), and extensions/APIs for customisation. Last but not least, they comply with the FDA 21 CFR Part 11 (USA) [17] and the EU Annex 11 [18]. These regulations require full audit trails, electronic signatures on completed records, witnessing and freezing, and measures to prevent records being deleted by their author.

High-end ELNs

High-end ELNs are tools that come as a module of a comprehensive laboratory management system [15] (e.g. Hivebench, Limsophy). In addition to all the features of specialised ELNs, they include a Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS) that allows complete tracking of samples and reagents through all experiments. They are also directly linked to laboratory equipment and can automatically deliver raw data and metadata from this equipment. Finally, high-end ELNs provide workflows and allow data mining and analysis of raw data within the ELN.

Further criteria to be considered

Other criteria to consider when selecting an ELN include those discussed earlier in this paper. You will need to choose between a proprietary and an open-source ELN; if you choose a proprietary ELN, it will need to provide an appropriate exit strategy/full export capabilities, including of the entire ELN. You will also need to choose between a cloud-hosted Software as a Service (SaaS) or a locally hosted, on-premises solution, and you should consider the performance and stability of both the ELN and the company/developer community (see Rule 2). You should also consider usability (i.e. clarity, intuitive operation, easy to navigate menus, drag and drop) (see Rule 3).

Other criteria include your lab's established practices and preferences, the security level of your data, your budget [3], whether you want a browser-based solution, the transparency and flexibility of the company/developer community, the possibilities for collaborative development and expansion, the background research discipline, and the location of the headquarters.

S2 Appendix. Test questionnaire

This questionnaire is broadly based on the ZB MED ELN Guide (pp 45 to 49) [6].

Lab requirements

Does the ELN allow you to:

- Import and process special scientific formats?
- Export and process special scientific formats?
- Create your own templates (with drop-down menus to choose from a specified vocabulary)?
- Import templates or offer preconfigured templates? If so, which formats are supported?
- Share templates
 - With members of your own research group?
 - With external members who have a licence for the same ELN?
 - With external members who have no ELN licence?
- Link to files outside the ELN?
- Work concurrently on the same documents as several other collaborators?

Does the ELN offer:

- The special data entry and processing aids you need (e.g., scientific calculator, formula editor, dictation devices, digital pen, animal module, antibodies module, plasmids module, strains and cells module)?
- Sample management and the possibility to create material databases within the ELN?
- Standard interfaces (e.g., connection to a Laboratory Information Management System (LIMS) or other software)?
- Collaboration functions (e.g., individual users and groups, role management)?

Usability

- Is the ELN easy to navigate?
- How easily can you access a folder you have uploaded and are now looking for?
- Are the options self-explanatory?
- Does the ELN allow you to insert images and tables?
- Does the ELN allow you to use any text formatting you want?
- Does the ELN allow for freehand drawing?
- Does the ELN organise data in a way that meets your needs?

- Are you confident the ELN will be easy to explain to senior lab members who are used to physical lab notebooks?
- Are you confident the ELN will be easy to explain to new lab members?

Good Research Practice (GRP)

Does the ELN allow you to:

- Search for keywords and experiments within the ELN using free text search, advanced search, database queries and special search queries (e.g., searches for chemical formulas and reactions)?
- Ensure evidentiary value (e.g., audit trail, electronic signature and time stamp)?
- Easily export backups? If yes, in which formats?
- Easily export the entire ELN (e.g., for archiving purposes, or to migrate it to another ELN)?

Does the ELN offer:

- Documentation and traceability in line with GSP?
- Compliance with special regulatory requirements (e.g., GxP, ISO, FERPA, HIPAA)?
- Access (at least “read only”) for a minimum of ten years?
- (In-built) archiving / backups?

Connection to Research Data Management (RDM) system

Does the ELN allow you to:

- Assign persistent identifiers (e.g., Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs))?
- Reference an open experiment or sample (e.g., with a Persistent Identifier (PID)), even if the folder structure changes in the future?

Does the ELN offer:

- Support for assigning metadata (e.g., input masks)?
- Automatic metadata harvesting (e.g., extraction from log files, export from Excel spreadsheets)?

- Integration of controlled vocabularies?
- A connection to repositories, publishing platforms, file sharing services?
- A connection to digital preservation systems?

IT and data security

Does the ELN allow you to:

- Protect sensitive data within the ELN?
- Store data locally at the institute or in the institute's own cloud?
- Run it on all operating systems (OS)?

Does the ELN offer:

- Application Programming Interfaces (APIs)?
- A deployment model: installation on the user's/institute's own server?
- Device-independent web-based access, also outside of your institute (e.g., via a VPN)?
- An exit strategy (outgoing migration)?
- Data migration from other systems (incoming migration)?

Miscellaneous

Does the ELN offer:

- A classroom edition for teaching?
- Default language/multi-language support?

The following aspects are important to you:

- ...
- ...
- ...